

WATSON INTEGRALLARINING UCH O‘LCHAMLI PANJARADAGI IKKI FERMIONLI SISTEMALARNING SHREDINGER OPERATORLARI XOS QIYMATLARINI TOPISHGA TADBIQI

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***Annotatsiya.** Schrödinger operatori kvant mexanikasining asosiy operatorlaridan biri bo‘lib, tizimning energetik holatini aniqlashda muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Operatorning xos qiymatlarini topish, ya‘ni tizimning energiya darajalarini aniqlash, kvant mexanikasining muhim masalalaridan biridir. Bunday masalalarni yechishda ko‘pincha integral hisoblash usullari, jumladan Watson integrallari, qo‘llaniladi. Bu integrallar o‘zining murakkab strukturalari bilan tanilgan bo‘lib, ular ma‘lum bir o‘zgaruvchilarga qarab funksiyalarni to‘g‘ri aniqlashda yordam beradi. Schrödinger operatorining xos qiymatlarini aniqlash uchun Watson integralini qo‘llash orqali tizimning energetik holatlarini hisoblash mumkin.*

***Kalit so‘zlar:** Tor, Watson integrali, Shredinger operatori, xos qiymat.*

Ushbu maqolada uch o‘lchamli panjara \mathbb{Z}^3 da $V_{\lambda\mu}$, $\lambda, \mu > 0$ potensial yordamida tasvirlashuvchi ikkita bir xil fermionli sistemaga mos $\hat{h}_{\lambda\mu} = \hat{h}_0 - \hat{v}_{\lambda\mu}$ Schrödinger operatorining $\sigma_{\text{ess}}(\hat{h}_{\lambda\mu})$ muhim spektridan chapda yoki o‘ngda xos qiymatlarining mavjudligini aniqlash hamda, aniq soni va joylashgan o‘rnini ta‘sir energiyasi $\lambda, \mu > 0$ parametrga bog‘liq ravishda topishga doir teoremlarni isbotlashda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadigan integrallarni qaraymiz.

Faraz qilamiz, $\mathbb{T}^1 = (-\pi, \pi]$ bo‘lsin. \mathbb{T}^1 da qo‘shish va songa ko‘paytirish amallarini haqiqiy sonlarni 2π modul bo‘yicha qo‘shish va songa ko‘paytirish sifatida kiritamiz, masalan

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\pi}{2} + \pi &= \frac{3\pi}{2} = -\frac{\pi}{2} \pmod{2\pi}, \\ 6 \cdot \frac{\pi}{5} &= 2\pi - \frac{4\pi}{5} = -\frac{4\pi}{5} \pmod{2\pi}.\end{aligned}$$

Ushbu to‘plam **bir o‘lchamli tor** deb ataladi. \mathbb{T}^d bilan d o‘lchamli tor, ya‘ni

$$\mathbb{T}^d = \underbrace{\mathbb{T}^1 \times \mathbb{T}^1 \times \dots \times \mathbb{T}^1}_{d \text{ marta}}$$

ni belgilaymiz.

d o‘lchamli tor \mathbb{T}^d da aniqlangan, Haar ma‘nosida o‘lchovga ega va

$$\int_{\mathbb{T}^d} |f(q)|^p dq < \infty$$

shartni qanoatlantiruvchi barcha $f: \mathbb{T}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ funksiyalarning chiziqli fazosini qaraymiz, bunda integralda o‘lchov Haar ma‘nosida olinadi va p tayinlangan musbat son. Elementlarni qo‘shish va songa ko‘paytirish odatdagi funksiyalarni qo‘shish va songa ko‘paytirish kabi kiritiladi. Hosil bo‘lgan fazo $L_p(\mathbb{T}^d)$ kabi belgilanadi. Demak, bu fazoning elementlari \mathbb{R}^d da aniqlangan va har bir o‘zgaruvchisi bo‘yicha 2π davrga ega bo‘lgan funksiyalardir.

Quyidagi integrallarni qaraymiz:

$$W_s = \frac{1}{\pi^3} \int_0^\pi \int_0^\pi \int_0^\pi \frac{dx dy dz}{3 - \cos x - \cos y - \cos z}, \quad (1)$$

$$I_1 = \frac{1}{8\pi^3} \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} \frac{\cos p_1}{3 - \cos p_1 - \cos p_2 - \cos p_3} dp, \quad (2)$$

$$I_2 = \frac{1}{8\pi^3} \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} \frac{\cos^2 p_1}{3 - \cos p_1 - \cos p_2 - \cos p_3} dp, \quad (3)$$

$$I_3 = \frac{1}{8\pi^3} \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} \frac{\cos p_1 \cos p_2}{3 - \cos p_1 - \cos p_2 - \cos p_3} dp. \quad (4)$$

(1) integral Watson integrali hisoblanib, uning son qiymati $W_s = 0.50546 20197$ dan iborat. Bu integral [2] adabiyotda uning hisoblanishlari va shu kabi integrallar [1]-[6] adabiyotlarda keltirilgan. (1) integraldan foydalanib (2)-(4) integrallarni o‘rganamiz. Bu integrallar uch o‘lchamli panjaradagi ikki fermionli sistemaga mos Shredinger operatorining xos qiymatlarini topishda muhim rol o‘ynaydi.

$$\varepsilon(p) = 3 - \cos p_1 - \cos p_2 - \cos p_3, \quad p \in \mathbb{T}^3,$$

$$I_1 = \frac{1}{8\pi^3} \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} \frac{\cos p_1}{\varepsilon(p)} dp = \frac{1}{8\pi^3} \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} \frac{\cos p_2}{\varepsilon(p)} dp = \frac{1}{8\pi^3} \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} \frac{\cos p_3}{\varepsilon(p)} dp,$$

$$I_2 = \frac{1}{8\pi^3} \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} \frac{\cos^2 p_1}{\varepsilon(p)} dp = \frac{1}{8\pi^3} \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} \frac{\cos^2 p_2}{\varepsilon(p)} dp = \frac{1}{8\pi^3} \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} \frac{\cos^2 p_3}{\varepsilon(p)} dp,$$

$$I_3 = \frac{1}{8\pi^3} \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} \frac{\cos p_1 \cos p_2}{\varepsilon(p)} dp = \frac{1}{8\pi^3} \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} \frac{\cos p_1 \cos p_3}{\varepsilon(p)} dp = \frac{1}{8\pi^3} \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} \frac{\cos p_2 \cos p_3}{\varepsilon(p)} dp$$

(2) integralni quyidagi ko‘rinishda yozamiz:

$$3I_1 = \frac{1}{8\pi^3} \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} \frac{3 - 3 + \cos p_1 + \cos p_2 + \cos p_3}{\varepsilon(p)} dp = \frac{1}{8\pi^3} \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} \frac{3 - \varepsilon(p)}{\varepsilon(p)} dp \Rightarrow$$

$$I_1 = \frac{1}{8\pi^3} \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} \frac{1}{\varepsilon(p)} dp - 1 = W_s - 1 = -0,4945379803.$$

Endi (3) va (4) integrallar orasidagi bog‘lanishni ko‘rib chiqamiz

$$\begin{aligned} 3I_2 + 6I_3 &= \frac{1}{8\pi^3} \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} \frac{\cos^2 p_1 + \cos^2 p_2 + \cos^2 p_3}{\varepsilon(p)} dp + \\ &+ \frac{1}{8\pi^3} \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} \frac{2 \cos p_1 \cos p_2 + 2 \cos p_1 \cos p_3 + 2 \cos p_2 \cos p_3}{\varepsilon(p)} dp = \\ &= \frac{1}{8\pi^3} \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} \frac{(3 - \varepsilon(p))^2}{\varepsilon(p)} dp = \frac{1}{8\pi^3} \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} \frac{9 - 6\varepsilon(p) + \varepsilon^2(p)}{\varepsilon(p)} dp = \\ &= \frac{1}{8\pi^3} \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} \frac{9}{\varepsilon(p)} dp - \frac{1}{8\pi^3} \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} 6 dp + \frac{1}{8\pi^3} \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} \varepsilon(p) dp = 9W_s - 3 = 1,5491581773. \end{aligned}$$

Demak, I_2 va I_3 integrallar quyidagicha bog‘lanishga ega

$$I_2 = 0,5163860591 - 2I_3.$$

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